

characterised as kaempferol by m.m.p., co-chromatography, microdegradation^{3,4} and spectroscopic examinations⁵.

Ethyl acetate extract on concentration gave a flavone glycoside, which when purified by column chromatography melted at 268° and analysed for C₂₂H₂₂O₁₁. On hydrolysis with mineral acid, it gave an aglycone C₁₆H₁₂O₆, m.p. 295°, and glucose. The aglycone has been found to be kaempferide (4'-methyl ether of kaempferol) by analysis, colour reactions, spectral data and preparation of derivatives. The glucose unit has been shown to be linked to 7-hydroxyl group by the study of spectral shift using aluminium chloride⁶ and sodium acetate⁷. The presence of glucose in the pyranose form has been proved by periodate oxidation and the presence of a β-glycosidic linkage has been confirmed by its hydrolysis with emulsin. Work on other compounds isolated from *Pterospermum heyneanum* is in progress.

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Study of Thallium (I)-Glycollate, Lactate and Mandelate Complexes.

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THALLOUS complexes with glycollic, lactic and mandelic acids have not been cited in the literature. In the present investigation author has therefore chosen these complexes for the study of their composition and stability.

E. Merck thalious nitrate and B.D.H. (Analar) glycollic, lactic and mandelic acids are used for preparing the solutions in double distilled water. Conductance measurements are done with "DORON" conductivity bridge with 1000 cycle WTW oscillator and dip type conductivity cell. Absorbance measurements are

done with the Beckman model DU quartz spectrophotometer using 5 mm light path absorption cells. All measurements are carried out at a temperature of 28 ± 0.5° and at a pH of 6.5.

The composition of the complexes are first studied by monovariation¹ method. 0.033M and 0.025M equimolar solutions were mixed keeping the volume of metal solution as 5ml and varying the volume of ligand solution making total volume equal in all the cases. Thallous ion forms 1 : 1 complexes with all the three ligands. The composition was further confirmed by Job's method² using conductance and absorbance as index properties. For conductance measurement 0.025M, 0.012M and for absorbance 0.05M equimolar solutions were employed.

The instability constant and hence the stability constant of the complexes are determined by Job's method². For conductance measurement 'P' (Molar concentration of ligand/Molar concentration of metal solution) was kept at 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 with C = 0.01M. For spectrophotometric study 0.02 M metal and 0.05M ligand solutions were mixed, and for each ligand readings were recorded at three different wave lengths according to suitability ranging from 245 to 280 nm.

The values of dissociation constants both by conductometric and spectrophotometric methods are in good agreement with each other and are reported to be 2.11 × 10⁻², 9.22 × 10⁻² and 11.7 × 10⁻² respectively for the thalious glycollate, -lactate and -mandelate complexes.

The change in the free energy of formation of glycollate, lactate and mandelate complexes by the equation F = -RT lnK are calculated to be -2.299, -1.421 and -1.279 K. cal per mole respectively at 28°.

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Titrimetric Determination of Copper(II) with Thioglycollic Acid.

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A method for the determination of copper(II) in aqueous solution is described based on the titration of a cupric salt solution with standard thioglycollic acid solution. Cupric ion oxidises thioglycollic acid to dithioglycollic acid with the simultaneous formation of cuprous mercaptide^{1,2}. The latter compound

complexes excess cupric ion leading to the formation of a mixed cuprous-cupric mercaptide which in the present case is violet. On adding thioglycollic acid the mixed mercaptide breaks and at the end point the violet colour is replaced by a permanent yellow precipitate of cuprous mercaptide. The overall process is represented by the following equation,

Although iodometry is a common procedure for the determination of copper(II), the method is vitiated by the presence of compounds that react with iodine liberated on adding potassium iodide to copper(II) salt solution. The thioglycollic acid method can tolerate a number of such compounds. No indicator is required for titration and the thioglycollic acid solution is to be checked only after each two weeks.

Experimental

Reagents: A 0.05M solution of copper(II) sulphate was prepared by dissolving a right amount of AnalaR sample in distilled water. Its strength was checked by iodometric titration. Less concentrated solutions were made by appropriate dilution.

An aqueous solution of 0.1M thioglycollic acid was prepared by dissolving an approximate volume of 98-99% pure sample. Its strength was determined by oxidising with a known excess of iodine solution followed by titrating the latter with standard thiosulphate³. Alternatively and if the same burette is to be used for filling thioglycollic acid, the following method may be used.

In a 150-ml Erlenmeyer flask 10 ml of 0.1 N iodate solution is taken and treated with 0.5g of potassium iodide plus 3ml of 1M sulphuric acid. The liberated iodine is diluted with 25ml of distilled water and titrated with thioglycollic acid being delivered from a 10-ml burette graduated in 0.02 ml. About 1 ml of 0.5% starch is added only when the solution of the flask is yellow and the blue complex is further titrated to colourless end point. The following reaction occurs

Procedure: A measured volume (about 10-30ml) of copper(II) salt solution (containing about 6-50mg of copper) is taken in a 150-ml Erlenmeyer flask. A 0.05M solution of thioglycollic acid is used, when the sample solution contains upto 23mg of copper and a 0.1M titrant for higher amounts. The contents of the flask are swirled regularly during titration. At the end point the deep violet complex first formed changes to a permanent yellow. Near the end-point the titrant is added slowly with vigorous shaking.

Results

Copper(II) salt with sulphate, nitrate, chloride or acetate may be directly titrated with thioglycollic acid. A pH of 4 is best suited for the titration. In the case

of copper(II) acetate the desired pH may be brought down by dropwise addition of dilute hydrochloric acid. Results for the determination of copper(II) are given in Table 1. It follows from the equation for the reaction

TABLE-1. DETERMINATION OF COPPER WITH THIOLYCOLLIC ACID

Taken	Copper (mg)	Found	± Diff. (mg)
6.40		6.39	- 0.01
12.80		12.72	- 0.08
18.55		18.50	- 0.05
25.60		25.52	- 0.08
30.42		30.49	+ 0.07
36.56		36.46	- 0.10
44.61		44.72	+ 0.11
50.80		51.06	+ 0.26

of copper(II) with thioglycollic acid that 1ml of 0.05M thioglycollic acid is equivalent to 1.5885 mg of copper. The proposed method is accurate to 0.3% with a standard deviation of 0.2%. Cinnamic acid, sodium formate, allyl alcohol, glycine, cystine and zinc, bromide, chloride and sulphite ions can be tolerated. Serious interference is caused by iron(III), lead(II), tin(II), silver(I) and mercury(II) ions.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Mercury(II) with Cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide

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SEVERAL β -ketoanilides have been recommended for the gravimetric determination of mercury(II)¹⁻³. This report describes the use of cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide as a reagent for the extraction spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II).